

panicle exertion, and grain sterility, and does not possess high salt tolerance.

F₁ plants were anther cultured and two dihaploid lines of each cross were produced. The lines are semidwarf, with better agronomic traits than IR4630-2-5-1-3. Ten plants of each line or variety per replication were used.

Pregerminated seeds were salinized at an EC of 12 dS/m with 1:1 ratio of NaCl and CaCl₂ and the salinity level maintained for 1 mo. Survival ranged from 21% for IR4630 to 94% for Pokkali (Fig. 1). Anther culture line IR51491-AC4-6 was quite tolerant of salinity, comparable with Pokkali and Nona Bokra.

In general, root length and root weight were more affected by salinity. IR51491-AC4-6 and IR51491-AC4-7 had longer and heavier roots than their parents IR4630 and Pokkali (Fig. 1). IR51500-AC9-7 and IR51500-AC11-1 were superior to their parents IR4630 and IR5657 in seedling height and root

2. Relative Na content and survival of anther culture lines IR51491 and IR51500 and their parents at salinity of 12 dS/m. IRRI. 1988.

length. IR51500-AC9-7 and IR51500-AC11-1 had heavier roots than tolerant check Nona Bokra.

Apparently, relative Na content was inversely related to percentage survival (Fig. 2). Pokkali and Nona Bokra, considered tolerant, showed the highest

survival rate and low relative Na content; IR4630, a moderately tolerant variety, had the lowest Na content. This suggests that the principle of salt tolerance in rice may be due to the ability of the plant to minimize Na absorption. □

Natural outcrossing of cytoplasmic male sterile line IR54752A in Indonesia

Satoto and B. Sutaryo, *Plant Breeding Division, Sukamandi Research Institute for Food Crops, Subang, West Java, Indonesia*

We studied the effect of number and distance of pollinator on the outcrossing rate of IR54752A during 1986-87 wet season, using a split-plot design with three replications. The main plot consisted of 2 levels of pollinator—1 and 6 rows. The subplot consisted of 4 pollinator distances—20, 40, 60, and 80 cm. IR54752B was seeded at the same rate 4 d later than IR54752A to synchronize flowering.

Five plants from each treatment were sampled before flowering. Row direction was arranged to be with the prevailing wind direction at flowering.

Number of pollinators did not significantly affect seed set and numbers of filled grains (Table 1). Hence, using one row of pollinators will be more advantageous than others, because the

Table 1. Seed set and filled grains/plant on cytotsterile line IR54752A by pollinator number.^a Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1986-87 wet season.

Pollinator number	Seed set (%)	Filled grains (no.)
1	5.7 a	65.6 a
6	6.4 a	89.0 a
CV (%)	19.3	49.5

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

cytoplasmic male sterile population can be further increased. Pollinator distance did not significantly affect seed set percentage or filled grains per plant. Filled grains per plant tended to decrease with distance (Table 2).

Table 2. Seed set and filled grains/plant on cytotsterile line IR54752A by pollinator distance.^a Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1986-87 wet season.

Pollinator distance (cm)	Seed set (%)	Filled grains (no.)
20	6.3 a	85.2 b
40	6.2 a	83.6 b
60	6.4 a	83.4 b
80	5.3 a	57.1 a
CV (%)	21.4	17.8

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Pollination at 80 cm depended on wind velocity. Low seed set probably was caused by the natural outcrossing in IR54752A. □

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